

On the Meso-structure Spatial Variability Characterizing and Geometric Modelling of Textile-Based Composite via Volume Imaging

Bin Yang^{1,2}, Jihui Wang², Philippe Causse³,
Cédric Béguin¹ & François Trochu¹

1. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Polytechnique Montréal
2. School of Material Science and Engineering, Wuhan University of Technology
3. Department of System Engineering, École de Technologie Supérieure

August 2, 2023

Digital Material Twin (DMT) - Virtual Lab

DMT = *Collection of actual physics-based models reflecting the exact structure of the physical part and operating conditions.*

- **detailed and accurate** geometrical modelling and meshing
- automatic tools to evaluate **quality**
- robust **numerical analysis**
- **multiscale** analysis
- real-time data from sensors in its physical implementation

Digital Material Twin in composites

Preform Digital Physics

Digital Composite Physics

Compressibility

Flow

...

Mesososcopic modelling technique

[1] Zeng et al., Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf. 2015

Geometrical simplification:

- General-purpose CAD software
- TexGen ^[1], etc.

[2] Verpoest et al., Compos Sci Technol. 2005

Mechanical prediction:

- WiseTex (minimum energy) ^[2]
- beam elements / digital element chain
- et cetera...

[3] Huang et al., Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf. 2019

Image-based modelling:

- Commercial: VG studio, Avizo ...
- Open source: ImageJ, Scikit-image ...
- In-house code

Objective

Develop a geometry modeling algorithm incorporating stochastic geometrical analysis and considering the local variation of materials.

Morphological representation of **fiber tow**

- **Tow representation** fibrous reinforcement
- **Statistical analysis** of geometrical features

Geometrical modeling and meshing of **fibrous preform**

- **3D reconstruction fabric**
- **Conformal and non-conformal meshing**

Outline

Experimental characterization

Fiber tow representation

3D preform reconstruction

Conclusion

Fibrous reinforcements investigated

8 dry circular plies
 Diameter : 25.4 mm
 Plies with the same orientation

Segmentation

Raw data

- Size: 12.25 mm × 15.55 mm × 5.63 mm
- Fiber volume fraction: 57 %

Point cloud

Semi-automated workflow:

Manual segmentation
on key slices

Interpolating the
segmented contour

Manual
refinement

Outline

Experimental method

Fiber tow representation

- Tow surface
- Tow trajectory
- Accuracy control

3D preform reconstruction

Conclusion

Parametric representation of tubular tow surface

Tow tubular surface

$$\hat{\Gamma}(s, t_i) = (X(s, t), Y(s, t), Z(s, t))$$

(s, t) : normalized geodesic distance
in **radial** and **axial** direction

Reduced to 2 dimensions

Extraction of tow trajectory

Trajectory $\gamma(t) = (x(t), y(t), z(t))$

1D parametric Kriging:

$$\gamma(t) = a(t) + W(t, \sigma^2)$$

- t : parameter
- σ^2 : nugget effect

$$\gamma(t) = (x(t), y(t), z(t)) \xrightarrow{\text{Tangent vector}} \gamma'(t) = (x'(t), y'(t), z'(t))$$

Cross-section identification

1. Parametric equation of tow surface:

$$\begin{cases} x(s_i, t) = k_1(s_i)^T \cdot S^{-1} \cdot P_x \cdot T^{-1} \cdot k_2(t) \\ y(s_i, t) = k_1(s_i)^T \cdot S^{-1} \cdot P_y \cdot T^{-1} \cdot k_2(t) \\ z(s_i, t) = k_1(s_i)^T \cdot S^{-1} \cdot P_z \cdot T^{-1} \cdot k_2(t) \end{cases}$$

Intersection between
an implicit object
and a parametric
object

2. Implicit equation of the plane:

- Centroid $P = (x_c, y_c, z_c)$
- Normal vector $\vec{n} = (a, b, c)$

$$a(x - x_c) + b(y - y_c) + c(z - z_c) = 0$$

Accelerated by
**Golden Section
Search**

Cross-section identification

Cross-section identification

Advantages

For each tow an analytical equation is provided:

- morphological operations
- reduce the data stored

Shrinkage induced by smoothing is avoided because:

- the estimator is constructed by minimizing variance (“best”)
- estimated values are weighted linear combinations of knowns
- it searches the combination with zero mean estimation error (“unbiased”)

Anisotropic smoothing:

- allows specifying different smoothing factors in axial and radial direction to attain anisotropic smoothing

Smoothing vs Shrinkage

Outline

Experimental method

Tow representation reinforcement

3D reconstruction reinforcement

- **Fiber tow assembling**
- **Mesopores distribution**

Conclusion

Labelled fiber tows

Flow and void formation simulation
in a dual scale structure:

- Fiber volume fraction (V_f)
- Fiber tow orientation
- Local variability and global conservation (V_f)

Spatial variability and vector information

Fiber volume fraction

Tangent vectors

In progressing: interpenetration between tows

Conformal & non-conformal meshes

($dx = 0.088$ mm, $dy = 0.11$ mm, $dz = 0.055$ mm)

Issue: too many elements \rightarrow simplification!

Outline

Experimental method

Tow representation reinforcement

3D reconstruction reinforcement

Conclusion

Conclusion

Tow contour

Tow trajectory

Local variability

Digital Material Twin

A basis for future numerical work based on high-fidelity models

One more thing ...

Composites: Part A 169 (2023) 107524

Performance evaluation of unidirectional molds used for measuring saturated transverse permeability of engineering textiles

Bin Yang^{a,b}, Yixun Sun^a, François Trochu^a, Cédric Béguin^a, Jihui Wang^b, Philippe Causse^{c,*}

^a Department of Mechanical Engineering, Research Center for High Performance Polymer and Composite Systems, Polytechnique Montréal, 2900 Boulevard Édouard Montpetit, Montréal, Québec H3T 1J4, Canada

^b School of Material Science and Engineering, Wuzhan University of Technology, 122 Luoshi Road, Honeshan, 430070 Wuzhan, PR China

^c Department of Mechanical Engineering

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Engineering textiles
Transverse permeability
Mold performance
Iterative framework

ut approaches revealed consider-
e analysis protocols makes quan-
iding approaches for evaluating
ility from conventional saturated
es affect flow capacity and lead to
e performance, a dimensionless
d on mold geometry and sample
intrinsic transverse permeability
h actual textiles. The first under-
inconsistency. Comparatively, the
ency for both molds.

Findings:

- support plate affects the measurement
- accuracy varies along material properties (thickness & anisotropy)
- potential underestimation of K_Z

Discharge coefficient, an indicator for:

- evaluation of mold performance
- comparison of different molds
- K_Z correction (from apparent to intrinsic)

Thank you!

Email: bin.yang@polymtl.ca

Blog: www.binyang.fun